

Situational leadership and its relationship to crisis management among Jordanian universities

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Feb 26, 2024

Revised Nov 3, 2024

Accepted Nov 20, 2024

Keywords:

Crisis management
Department heads
Faculty members
Jordanian universities
Situational leadership

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the extent of situational leadership practice and its correlation with crisis management among heads of academic departments in Jordanian universities, as perceived by faculty members. Employing a descriptive-correlational approach, the study sampled 405 faculty members in Jordanian universities for the spring semester of 2022/2023. To collect data situational leadership scales and crisis management scale were used. The findings revealed a high degree of situational leadership practice and crisis management effectiveness among department heads. Moreover, a statistically significant relationship between situational leadership and crisis management is observed. The study suggests selecting department heads with strong competencies and involving faculty members in crisis management courses to enhance overall effectiveness.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Leadership is important in educational institutions because it is inextricably linked to the intricate network of human interactions that exist inside organizations. Recognizing subordinates as critical assets within an organization emphasizes the importance of leadership in promoting their well-being, nurturing their development, and facilitating their training. This leadership role is critical for aligning institutions with global innovations and shifting paradigms. It serves to guide an organization toward its goals, reinforcing positive features while minimizing negative aspects. Furthermore, successful leadership in educational contexts entails skillfully handling work-related issues and settling conflicts among colleagues [1].

An organization's ability to succeed or fail is largely determined by its leadership, which plays a crucial role in the organization's framework. Leadership Life Cycle Theory states that the advent of situational leadership in 1969 brought about a revolutionary change in leadership paradigms. They stressed how important it is for managers who want to use situational leadership to carefully examine their workplace and then adjust their behavior accordingly. If this objective is not met, it is anticipated that the strategy will have little bearing on how their efforts turn out [2].

The researchers explained on this concept, presenting an updated model of situational leadership. This contemporary framework accentuates the influential role of leaders and highlights the significance of adaptability and employing leadership styles that correspond to the varying capabilities of followers within specific work environments. Situational leadership, in essence, entails the modification of a leader's style in response to prevailing circumstances and attitudes. Recognizing the absence of a singular leadership style universally applicable across all workplaces, this approach advocates for a dynamic adaptation of leadership

styles contingent upon the competencies and knowledge of subordinates, as well as the demands intrinsic to the task at hand [3].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Situational leadership denotes a set of principles, concepts, or directives deemed fitting for prevailing circumstances and congruent with their inherent characteristics [4]. Situational leadership entails a recognition that leaders possess the capacity to employ diverse leadership styles contingent upon specific scenarios, with each situation necessitating distinct considerations [5]. The situational theory explains why leadership works in organizational settings and provides a common framework for leaders to adjust their behavior to the needs of certain circumstances. Effective leadership emerges when a leader skillfully assesses the degree of expertise that team members possess in certain tasks and then employs an appropriate style of leadership. The primary responsibility of university administration is to achieve this goal by revitalizing administrative leadership and its operations. Universities therefore want to improve performance in general and in particular the performance of their academic leaders. It becomes necessary to tackle these issues in order to promote growth and development as a result of the erratic and increasing changes in the global environment [4].

The four phases of situational leadership are described: the initial stage (directing and informing) involves the leader putting success over interpersonal relationships, frequently turning to a directive strategy. In this stage, subordinates may struggle to complete assigned responsibilities and there may be interpersonal conflicts. The following stage, “exchange and guidance,” is distinguished by the leader clarifying tasks and cultivating relationships. Subordinates with some required knowledge and abilities nonetheless lack confidence and require instruction, similar to a persuasion-oriented approach [6]. Transitioning to the “participation and support” stage, subordinates who have proved ability demand help and encouragement, yet reluctance to undertake assigned tasks may occur. The leader strives to understand the reasons for the resistance and uses a participative persuasion style to foster cooperation [7]. Finally, the “delegation” stage occurs when subordinates demonstrate competence in executing duties independently. In this phase, the leader uses a delegated leadership style, giving the subordinate autonomy and task freedom [8].

Situational leadership employs several strategies to address crises and mitigate their impact on the institution. One such strategy involves simplifying and facilitating procedures, acknowledging the urgent and severe nature of crises, necessitating swift and decisive action that diverges from standard administrative procedures. Crisis management, contrary to a spontaneous or reactive approach, requires adherence to an appropriate administrative framework centered on planning, organizing, directing, and follow-up tasks to ensure success and safeguard against unforeseen developments [9].

Furthermore, an essential aspect of crisis management is the assessment of the crisis situation. This involves a comprehensive identification of the forces influencing the crisis, understanding its drivers, and evaluating the capacities and capabilities of the authority responsible for crisis management. Accurate data on the crisis dimensions and projections of its potential development are crucial elements in this evaluation [10]. Setting priorities is another strategic imperative in situational leadership during a crisis. Plans and alternatives are devised based on evaluations of current and anticipated events, ordered according to predetermined criteria and priorities. This strategic approach aids in effective crisis management by providing a structured framework for decision-making [11].

Establishing and maintaining communication channels with relevant parties is emphasized in crisis management. Open lines of communication facilitate the acquisition of necessary information, immediate monitoring of crisis events, understanding the behavior of involved parties, and assessing the outcomes of such behavior [11]. Additionally, a constant presence at event locations is deemed indispensable in crisis management. Being physically present ensures the availability of sufficient data for decision-makers, offers insights into ongoing events, and leaves positive psychological impressions. This approach underscores the significance of information in crisis management and its role in fostering a connection with employees and the community. In the administrative process, whether in crisis management or within a crisis task force, the delegation of authority is regarded as central. Delegation is considered the “beating heart” of the administrative process and the lifeblood of the crisis management cycle [12].

The delegation of powers involves conferring the requisite authority upon each team member assigned to crisis management tasks, coupled with an understanding of the associated duties and responsibilities. Delegating authority to employees' entails encouraging wholehearted engagement and accountability, premised on the leader's trust, rendering delegation untenable for those unwilling to assume responsibility [13]. A comprehensive media plan is deemed crucial in crisis management by situational leadership, recognizing the pivotal role of the media in influencing the efficacy of crisis management stages. It is recommended that a well-defined media policy be in place before, during, and after a crisis. An essential

aspect of this plan is the appointment of a qualified official spokesperson, entrusted with disseminating accurate information aligned with the institution's objectives throughout various stages of crisis management [14]. Acknowledging the ubiquity of crises in contemporary existence, the imperative to address them collectively arises, given their impact on daily life. The prevalence of crises, attributed to changes in economic, social, and educational environments, coupled with institutional limitations in adopting adaptive management models, engenders concerns for educational institutions, particularly universities. The inevitability of crises underscores the need for proactive crisis management planning, irrespective of an institution's size, nature of activity, or sector affiliation [15]. In order to effectively confront crises, university crisis management unit staff members must possess requisite planning and scientific awareness. Continuous learning and professional development are emphasized for staff members to enhance their capabilities and contribute meaningfully to crisis planning and management [16].

Situational leadership within the context of crises is anticipated to exert a substantial influence on the crisis management process [2]. These crises necessitate heightened involvement from all departments, including the human resources department, to effectively manage their impact on both societies and institutions. The discourse surrounding crisis management has proliferated due to the diversity of disciplines, opinions, and conceptualizations. Varying perspectives on crisis management have emerged among researchers, holding the interest for management experts, politicians, psychologists, and sociologists alike [17]. Sharif and Mohamed [18] posited that crisis management is an independent management domain centered on the anticipation of crisis locations and trends. This approach involves creating a conducive environment for addressing crises using scientific administrative tools, mitigating negative aspects, and maximizing positive outcomes across the three stages of a crisis: pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis.

According to Al-Azzam [19], crisis management in an organizational context involves an entity's capacity to confront crises utilizing diverse scientific and administrative instruments while leveraging any drawbacks to its advantage. The definition of crisis management in the university context, as elucidated by Nashwan *et al.* [20] encompasses methods and focused activities undertaken by senior leaders in higher education. These leaders employ techniques and tactics to anticipate, manage, prevent, and create suitable scenarios for university crises. The overarching goal is to control, confront, contain, reduce losses, minimize negative effects, and capitalize on outcomes to prevent future occurrences, thereby enhancing the university's interests and future objectives while maintaining its reputation for excellence.

Various factors underscore the importance of crisis management for educational institutions and elucidate the advantages it can offer [21]. These include averting dangerous consequences resulting from unpreparedness for crises, reducing uncertainty around crisis existence, expediting the return to normalcy post-crisis, and potentially preventing crises. Additionally, crisis management contributes to creating a psychological environment that counters crisis fear, dispels rumors, and mitigates undesirable behaviors. Moreover, it facilitates the development of a skilled and effective team capable of enhancing organizational effectiveness, managing crisis effects, and deriving valuable lessons from crises.

Crisis management goes through many stages, as indicated by Stowe and Darbal [22]: i) Detecting warning signs: the first step in crisis management is to establish a team that plans and accurately predicts the future using its tools, such as scenarios, and simulations. This stage refers to before the beginning of the crisis, and it is represented by the institution's ability to respond to any indicators. Therefore, the administration monitors and identifies indicators or symptoms that indicate the possibility of a crisis; ii) Prevention and readiness: in order to lessen the harm caused by the crisis while continuing to work to prevent it from happening, the institution's administration gets ready for it and then to face it; iii) Limiting or containing damage: the management must put the created plans into action, begin employing all available instruments and means, better utilize available resources, and limit the crisis's damage during this stage, which is the crisis' peak; iv) Restoring activity: it is the stage where the crisis starts to gradually subside, allowing the administration to regain equilibrium and carry out its regular tasks as it did before the crisis occurred. The administration has also pinpointed the root causes of the crisis, allowing it to offer some workable solutions; and v) Learning: this stage starts after the crisis has passed, and it is characterized by an evaluation of the strategies and tactics employed to deal with it. It also involves learning from the experience and building on it in order to be able to prevent similar crises from happening again in the future.

Various scholars have undertaken extensive examinations of situational leadership. For instance, Al-Taymah [12] conducted a study in Jordanian universities, revealing a consensus among female leaders and subordinates that the delegated style of situational leadership is predominantly practiced. Alwan [9] explored the role of situational leadership in the stages of university crisis management, elucidating its contribution to mitigating or addressing crises in a manner aligning with institutional interests. Furthermore, Alwan [9] identified a correlational relationship between situational leadership and the various stages of crisis management. Al-Babtain [13] research similarly indicated a high degree of adherence to situational leadership methods. Al-TaHER [23] focused on emphasizing key situational leadership theories, and evaluating their contributions to human resources in attaining professional competence.

Despite the widespread application of situational leadership in leadership development and training, critiques have surfaced, shedding light on its limitations and providing a more nuanced understanding of its overall advantages in leadership study and practice. Al-Obaid [24] investigation underscored the prevalence of situational leadership practice. However, Al-Abadi research [25] suggested a moderate need to enhance the performance of academic leaders in private Jordanian universities through the application of the situational leadership theory. According to the perspectives of both academic leaders and faculty members, there exists a medium-level need for improvement in the performance of academic leaders in Jordanian private universities concerning situational leadership [4]. Specifically, planning and implementation were rated highest but to a medium degree, while monitoring and evaluation received a lower ranking.

A multitude of scholars have engaged in research pertaining to crisis management, as evidenced by Daniel investigation [26]. The primary objective of this study was to discern optimal organizational practices in crisis leader communication within the context of colleges and universities, specifically during and following crises. The study aimed to identify effective communication strategies that mitigate or prevent damage in such scenarios. The research yielded several outcomes, with a paramount conclusion highlighting the existence of 11 communication strategies specifically designed for addressing crises within colleges, universities, and their personnel in response to the challenges they confront.

Slater research [27] uncovered that university presidents possess awareness regarding the definition of a crisis, their responsibilities before, during, and after crises, the importance of their positions, and the availability of institutional resources. These aspects are identified as crucial elements in effective crisis management. Mehta and Wang [28] focused on the position of the library during the COVID-19 crisis, particularly examining the challenges faced by the Bridgewater State University library in Massachusetts in delivering digital services. The study outlined unexpected issues arising from the epidemic, detailed modifications made to existing services, and introduced new procedures to support the overall teaching and learning environment of the university.

Moerschell and Novak [29] concluded from their data that the frequency and complexity of critical events necessitate the implementation of a comprehensive crisis management system in university leadership. This is crucial to prevent prolonged business interruptions and potential reputational damage. Research by McNamara [30] investigated the effects of COVID-19 on leadership in higher education institutions, utilizing interviews with leaders from conservatories in Australia, the UK, and the USA. The study revealed high-frequency words and subject collections, leading to the proposal of a mindful leadership model to enhance the adaptability of leaders in responding to structural weaknesses in higher education.

Dajani research [31] aimed to understand how adaptive leadership techniques influenced organizational resilience in the Egyptian academic community during a change management crisis. A tool was developed to assist universities in enhancing their capacity to recover from crises and disasters in an academic context. Al-Deeb [32] emphasized the importance of educating the university community about the necessity of developing a culture of crisis management planning and providing crisis management teams at colleges with the required resources, personnel, and organizational capacity. According to Sharif and Mohamed [18], administrators practiced the dimensions of strategic intelligence to a moderate degree, with the second dimension, "Future Vision" ranking last. The study recommended creating crisis management teams in Egyptian universities, presented using Assiut University as a model. Abusleima [21] identified nine key requirements for crisis management in Egyptian universities, including leadership, proactive crisis management, strategic planning, organizational structure, work systems, resource flow, multifunctional communication, work environment, psychological atmosphere, and strategic sensitivity.

Nashwan *et al.* [20] indicated a positive relationship between human capital and university crisis management with statistical significance. Al-Otaibi [15] reported excellent crisis management at Umm Al-Qura University during the COVID-19 pandemic, with acknowledgment of the university's commitment and effective contribution to community responsibility programs across various fields. However, challenges were noted, primarily a lack of human capital. The motivation of this study is the experience in the educational field, in addition to the lack of previous studies on the Jordanian environment in particular and the Arab environment in general, which is reflected in a better understanding of the relationship between situational leadership and crisis management among heads of academic departments in Jordanian universities.

Scholars within academic departments, serving as faculty members, have noted the presence of numerous administrative challenges. Some department heads adopting the situational leadership style have been identified as potentially offering a resolution to these challenges. Given the current global changes and the universities' aspirations for total quality principles and global recognition, there is a need for leaders possessing transitional qualities. These leaders should demonstrate resilience and competence while assuming responsibility. The overarching goal is to advance in the global university rankings. Furthermore, these leaders should adeptly manage crises, minimizing institutional losses by fostering collaborative efforts among department personnel to achieve both public and private objectives. This study aimed to answer the

following questions: i) What is the extent of situational leadership practice among academic department heads in Jordanian universities as perceived by faculty members? (Q1); ii) What is the perceived level of crisis management among academic department heads in Jordanian universities as assessed by faculty members? (Q2); and iii) Is there a statistically significant correlation between the application of situational leadership and the effectiveness of crisis management among academic department heads in Jordanian universities as perceived by faculty members? (Q3).

3. METHOD

3.1. Population and sample

The study population consisted of all faculty members in Jordanian universities, namely the Hashemite University, Yarmouk University, and Mutah University; their number reached 3,250 people. The study sample consisted of 405 faculty members, and a percentage of approximately 13% of the total community, including 237 males, and 168 females, as well as those who are in the rank of professor is 141, associate professor is 133, and assistant professor is 131. Among them are 189 humanities colleges and 216 scientific colleges.

3.2. Research instruments

Following a comprehensive review of theoretical literature and prior research, the researchers formulated a questionnaire with the overarching objective of assessing situational leadership and its correlation with crisis management among academic department heads in Jordanian universities from the perspective of faculty members. The instrument designed to measure situational leadership drew inspiration from several pertinent studies [4], [9], [12], [25], which delved into the subject of situational leadership. Conversely, the tool developed to evaluate the level of crisis management among academic department heads in Jordanian universities found its basis in a selection of earlier studies addressing crisis management. These studies included contributions from several research [18], [20], [21], [32].

A cohort of arbitrators drawn from both public and private universities in Jordan was enlisted to evaluate the initial version of the study tool, ensuring its validity. The arbitrators were tasked with scrutinizing the tool's alignment with the established objectives, assessing the questionnaire's construction integrity, and providing insights into the appropriateness and clarity of its sections and paragraphs. Their valuable opinions were sought regarding the congruence of the questionnaire's content with the areas it purported to measure. The questionnaire employed a five-point Likert scale (5=very high, 4=high, 3=medium, 2=low, 1=very low). Classification of responses was facilitated by averaging the computerized scores and utilizing a three-tiered categorization plan: low (1-2.33), medium (2.34-3.67), and high (3.68-5).

To verify the reliability of the study instrument, the researchers applied it to a group outside the study sample, which consisted of 31 faculty members from the study community and they used Cronbach's alpha coefficient. The Cronbach's alpha of situational leadership was 0.91 and 0.82, 0.81, 0.71, and 0.87 respectively for leadership skills, leadership styles, participating in making decisions, and situational planning. While the reliability coefficient for the crisis management scale was 0.89.

3.3. Data collection and analysis

The data collection process for this study involved visits to faculty members in Jordanian universities. Prior to participation, faculty members were required to complete a consent form, expressing their willingness to engage in the study. Subsequently, the analysis was conducted utilizing SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistical measures, specifically arithmetic means and standard deviation, were employed. Additionally, inferential statistics were employed, with the calculation of the correlation coefficient utilizing Pearson's correlation coefficient.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Results of Q1

Regarding the initial inquiry, namely, the extent of situational leadership practice among academic department heads in Jordanian universities from the standpoint of faculty members, the response was derived through the calculation of arithmetic means and standard deviations. These measures were computed individually for each field and collectively for all fields. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 indicates that academic department heads within Jordanian universities exhibit a high level of engagement in situational leadership practices, as evidenced by their responses, which yielded an arithmetic mean of 3.69 and a standard deviation of 0.87. Notably, the domain of leadership skills demonstrated the highest arithmetic mean at 3.81, accompanied by a considerable standard deviation of 0.91. Following closely, the field of leadership styles obtained the second-highest arithmetic mean of 3.73, coupled

with a substantial standard deviation of 0.88. The field of participation in decisions secured the third position with an arithmetic mean of 3.60 and a standard deviation of 0.92, reflecting a moderate degree of engagement. Concluding the assessment, the field of situational planning received a medium score, recording an arithmetic mean of 3.54 and a standard deviation of 0.94.

Table 1. Mean and standard deviations for situational leadership

Variables	Rank	Mean	SD	Degree
Leadership skills	1	3.81	0.91	High
Leadership styles	2	3.73	0.88	High
Participating in decision making	3	3.60	0.92	Medium
Situational planning	4	3.54	0.94	Medium
Situational leadership		3.69	0.87	High

3.2. Results of Q2

To address the second inquiry pertaining to the assessment of crisis management levels among academic department heads in Jordanian universities from the faculty members' perspective, arithmetic means and standard deviations were computed. These calculations aimed to gauge the perceived level of crisis management among the heads of academic departments, as reported by the sampled faculty members. The findings revealed a high level of crisis management, evidenced by an arithmetic mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 0.70. This numerical representation substantiates the elevated standard of crisis management observed in the study.

3.3. Results of Q3

To address this inquiry, the study sample's responses were subjected to analysis using the Pearson correlation coefficient. This statistical measure was employed to ascertain the correlation between the degree of situational leadership practice and crisis management. The outcomes of this analysis are presented in Table 2. The table presents the Pearson correlation coefficient outcomes derived from the study sample's responses regarding the interplay between situational leadership and the proficiency in crisis management exhibited by heads of academic departments in Jordanian universities. The results indicate a notably positive correlation between these variables, as evidenced by a correlation coefficient value of 0.680, which is statistically significant (p -value=0.00). Moreover, the correlation coefficients between faculty members' perspectives on crisis management and the various facets of situational leadership practice by department heads (specifically, in the areas of leadership skills, leadership styles, participation in decision-making, and situational planning) were found to be 0.620, 0.627, 0.665, and 0.669, respectively. All these correlations exhibit strong, direct associations and are statistically significant (p -value=0.00).

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficient between situational leadership and crisis management

Variables	Crisis management
Leadership skills	0.62*
Leadership styles	0.62*
Participating in decision making	0.66*
Situational planning	0.66*
Situational leadership	0.68*

Note: * p =0.01

3.4. Discussion

This observation is explicable through a survey conducted among academics at Jordanian universities, wherein the responses to the study tool regarding the overall degree of situational leadership practice were consistently high. This outcome underscores the department heads' confidence in their colleagues, their adherence to rules and instructions, and the application thereof, fostering a culture of mutual respect. This result can also be explained by the knowledge of the heads of departments the positives of this type of leadership style that achieves the university's goals in a successful crisis management style. An inclusive and considerate department head, embracing modern democratic administrative principles, is integral to cultivating a cohesive work environment wherein the collective pursuit of shared objectives becomes paramount [6]. This aligns with the respondents' affirmations in "leadership skills" fields ranking highest with a high degree. This suggests faculty members' satisfaction with the demonstrated leadership skills, correlating positively with heightened performance, creativity, and the attainment of departmental and

collegiate goals. Furthermore, the field of "leadership styles" claimed the second-highest rank, attesting to positive responses from faculty members toward department heads and affirming the adaptability and effective management in confronting diverse situations. Such flexibility resonated positively in the study sample's evaluations of department heads' situational leadership practices [4].

Conversely, the field of "participation in decision-making" ranked penultimate with a medium degree. This positioning signifies faculty members' high confidence in the department head's ability to make accurate decisions related to the department, driven by their knowledge, experience, and trust in the department head, contributing to job security and psychological comfort. The apparent obstacle arises from the scheduling of faculty members' lectures on weekdays and the spacing of lecture times, hindering their participation in matters requiring collective engagement. The precision and efficacy in faculty member selection were emphasized to align with university goals and facilitate flexible management of department affairs by a department head well-versed in situational leadership, echoing insights [5]. Finally, the field of "situational planning" ranked lowest among the domains, also with a medium degree. This positioning reflects the department head's extensive experience, adept situational leadership practices, and administrative acumen, resulting in a nuanced approach to handling circumstances that demand less planning and more immediate decision-making. Given the prevalent high degree of situational leadership practice among department heads in Jordanian universities, these findings synergize cohesively. The congruence between this study's findings and other previous studies [4], [9], [12], [24], further validates the observed trends.

This outcome can be elucidated by considering the results obtained from both the first and second questions of the study. The initial question revealed a high level of situational leadership practice, while the subsequent question indicated a similarly elevated level of crisis management. The coexistence of a situational leader is conducive to adept decision-making and the application of wisdom in leadership, enabling effective crisis management. A situational leader demonstrates the capability to navigate departmental challenges with administrative flexibility, minimizing potential harm. This proficiency is reflected in the department's success in fulfilling tasks and responsibilities at the departmental level, showcasing its overall efficacy. The alignment between the observed high levels of situational leadership practice and crisis management reinforces the credibility of the study sample's responses to the research instrument. The pivotal role of a sincere and capable department head in crisis management is underscored, emphasizing the need for faculty members to earnestly delegate crisis management responsibilities to a competent leader who commands the respect, appreciation, and confidence of their colleagues. Faculty members are encouraged to direct their responses in a manner that recognizes and supports effective crisis management for the department's collective benefit.

This result can also be explained by the fact that within the duties of the head of the department under the job description to exercise his role and management in crisis management in the department to ensure the success of the department's work, so he was chosen for this role within a large group of members of the department to improve crisis management for the success of the department and the success of the level of college management in general. The findings of the third question align with the outcomes of several prior studies [18], [21], [26]–[29], [32]. The third question sought to explore, from the faculty members' standpoint, the association between the degree of situational leadership and the practice of crisis management by heads of academic departments in Jordanian universities.

This observed correlation can be elucidated by the effectiveness of situational leadership across diverse scenarios and timely application, which plays a pivotal role in crisis management. The higher the prevalence of academic department heads adept in situational leadership, the more pronounced is the department's efficacy in crisis management. To ensure effective management and adept responses to varied situations, universities are advised to judiciously select department heads possessing situational leadership skills. A situational leader fosters an optimal learning environment, demonstrating a vested interest in the professional development of colleagues, fostering a sense of belonging and collaboration. This collective effort contributes to achieving excellence and creativity within the department. These findings reinforcing the correlation between situational leadership and the stages of crisis management [9], [20].

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers advocate for the imperative for Jordanian university administrations to exhibit careful consideration in appointing department heads who exhibit traits associated with situational leadership. This strategic selection is deemed essential for steering departments towards desired globalization objectives. Moreover, there is a recommendation to augment the knowledge base of faculty members regarding crisis management through active participation in educational initiatives such as courses, seminars, and lectures. Furthermore, it is suggested to cultivate and enhance situational leadership styles among academic department heads. Additionally, the proposal involves instituting an annual award to recognize and commend distinguished department heads who excel in situational leadership. Lastly, the

researchers encourage the undertaking of further studies and research within Jordanian universities to explore the nuances of situational leadership and its correlations with various variables, including problem-solving capabilities and administrative creativity.

The authors suggest that the high degree of situational leadership practice among department heads in Jordanian universities is a significant factor contributing to effective crisis management within academic departments. The authors emphasize the importance of department heads embracing modern democratic administrative principles and exhibiting inclusive and considerate leadership styles. This approach fosters a cohesive work environment where faculty members feel satisfied with their leadership and are more likely to perform at heightened levels of creativity and efficiency.

Furthermore, the authors highlight the correlation between situational leadership skills and the ability to navigate crises effectively. They argue that department heads with adept situational leadership skills are better equipped to handle diverse scenarios, leading to improved crisis management outcomes. The authors suggest that universities should prioritize the selection of department heads who possess strong situational leadership abilities to ensure effective management and response to various situations. Overall, the author supports the idea that situational leadership plays a crucial role in crisis management within academic departments and underscores the importance of selecting leaders who can effectively navigate challenges while fostering a collaborative and supportive work environment.

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